

Supporting Information for “X-ray Coulomb Counting” to understand electrochemical systems

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Table S 1 summarizes X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray reflectivity (XRR), and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) techniques across the main geometries and modalities, including probe size, information depth, spatial resolution, advantages and limitations, and experimental constraints. We stress that many more specialized geometries and modalities are nowadays available at 4th generation light sources — including tomographic modalities of various techniques — and hope this will help readers select the most appropriate technique for their specific electrochemical questions.

Table S 1: Overview of major X-ray techniques and associated modalities used in electrochemical studies.

Technique	Primary Information	Geometry	Information Depth	Spatial Resolution	Advantages	Limitations	Experimental Constraints
XRD (Transmission)	Long-range crystalline order	Transmission	Bulk (μm – mm)	Beam-size dependent (mm – μm ; nm possible)	Quantitative phase analysis; <i>operando</i> full-cell compatibility	Insensitive to amorphous phases	Modified cells with X-ray transparent windows (unless high energy X-rays)
GI-XRD	Surface sensitive structural order	Grazing incidence	nm – tens of nm	Laterally averaged (footprint-limited)	Interface-sensitive structural analysis	Requires smooth surfaces	Specialized grazing-incidence cell; precise angular alignment
XRR	Film thickness; electron density; interfacial roughness	Specular low-angle reflectivity	Few hundred nm	Vertical: sub- nm ; laterally averaged	Sub- nm interface resolution; quantitative thin-film modeling	Requires smooth, laterally homogeneous films	Specialized reflectivity cell; unsuitable for rough composite electrodes
XAS (Transmission)	Element-specific oxidation state, local structure	Transmission	Bulk	Beam-size dependent	Quantitative bulk absorption; linear response	Limited sensitivity to minority species	Modified cells with X-ray transparent windows; sample thickness optimization
XAS (Fluorescence)	Element-specific oxidation state, local structure	Fluorescence detection	Bulk	Beam-size dependent	High sensitivity; suitable for thick samples and dilute species	Self-absorption effects	Modified cells with X-ray transparent windows
X-ray Microscopy	Spatially resolved composition/chemistry	Transmission or fluorescence with focused beam (or full-field)	Bulk	μm – tens of nm	Direct heterogeneity mapping	Flux-limited; long acquisition times	Requires focused beam; thin or windowed cells